

eCHARGE
4DRIVERS

D8.2

eCharge4drivers website

www.echarge4drivers.eu

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 875131 (Innovation Action)

Work Package	8
Task	8.2
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Dissemination Level	Public
Status	Final
Due date	30/09/2020
Document Date	14/10/2020
Version Number	1.0

Quality Control

	Name	Organisation	Date
Editor	Sara Jane Weeks	ERTICO	10/09/2020
Peer review 1	Fotis Manesis	BFS	18/09/2020
Peer review 2	Jaume Roca	BSM	09/10/2020
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DOCUMENT HISTORY

Version	Date	Editor	Revisions
0.1	28/07/20	Sara Jane Weeks and Carla Coppola (ERTICO)	First draft sent to ERTICO's Communication Manager for inputs
0.2	31/07/20	Sara Jane Weeks (ERTICO)	Feedback implemented and second draft sent to POLIS and ICCS
0.3	4/09/20	Laura Babio (POLIS), Barbara Basdeki, Niki Georgiou (ICCS)	Contributions provided by ICCS and POLIS
0.4	9/09/20	Sara Jane Weeks (ERTICO)	Comments addressed
0.5	21/09/20	Alessandro Rinaldi (POLIBA) and Fotis Manesis (BFS)	Document updated based on POLIBA's and BFS' revisions
0.6	8/10/20	Jaume Roca (BSM)	Revisions provided by BSM as peer reviewer
1.0	12/10/20	Sara Jane Weeks (ERTICO)	Final version ready for submission to EC

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

Abbreviation	Meaning
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
EV	Electric Vehicle
GDPR	European General Data Protection Regulation
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
kW	Kilowatt
TEN-T	Trans-European Transport Network
WP	Work Package

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

eCharge4Drivers' website www.echarge4drivers.eu has been designed to represent the project in a complete, transparent and user-friendly manner. The website will be an important dissemination tool for eCharge4Drivers, as it will contain all the necessary information on the project and will be constantly updated with the latest information. It will be the project's main channel to the outside world, providing information on eCharge4Drivers objectives, partners, methodologies, results, publications, news and success stories.

The website's design has been carefully selected to follow eCharge4Drivers' brand identity: all visual elements have been created by deconstructing the project's logo and placing its components in the website's space, to create a well recognisable visual pattern while browsing among eCharge4Drivers' information.

The website includes several dedicated sections in order to be as complete as possible. After its launch in M3 (August 2020), the website includes information about the project's objectives, the consortium, the pilot sites and TEN-T Corridors, the social media links and the contact details. An acknowledgment to the EU co-funding accompanied by the EU flag is displayed on the homepage.

Some of the sections, which content will be available at a later stage in eCharge4Drivers' implementation (such as events, news, deliverables, etc.), are going to be hidden, even though they are already part of the website's structure and functionality. These sections are Publications, Presentations, Video gallery and Deliverables. This content will be published as soon as it will be available.

The website will be updated on a regular basis and may also be revised as the project progresses. eCharge4Drivers' social media accounts, a Twitter account and a LinkedIn company page will actively advance the project's dissemination activities and serve as reflector of the website's content.

1 INTRODUCTION

eCharge4Drivers is an H2020 project running from June 2020 to May 2024 and deployed by a consortium of 32 partners. Charging an electric vehicle (EV) is still not as convenient as refuelling a conventional vehicle, potentially posing a barrier to increase the market uptake of EVs. eCharge4Drivers works to substantially improve the EV charging experience within cities and for long trips. The project will develop and demonstrate user-friendly charging stations and innovative charging solutions as well as smart charging services for the users. By capturing users' perceptions and expectations on the various charging options and their mobility and parking habits, eCharge4Drivers will organise demonstrations in 10 areas across Europe, including metropolitan areas and Trans-European Transport Network (TEN-T) corridors. Charging stations in these areas will offer user-friendly and convenient functionalities for EV drivers of passenger and light vehicles and motorcycles, such as direct payment methods and bigger, user-friendly displays. Using the knowledge generated, the project will also propose an EV Charging Location Planning Tool, fostering the broad implementation of charging infrastructure in Europe.

1.1 Purpose of the deliverable

This deliverable provides a description of eCharge4Drivers' website and outlines its structure, design and functionalities.

1.2 Intended audience

This is a public document, and can also be consulted by the European Commission, eCharge4Drivers' consortium partners and external stakeholders.

1.3 Relation with other work packages/deliverables

This document is complementary to eCharge4Drivers Deliverable 8.1 Communication and Dissemination Strategy. Deliverable 8.1 presents a complete communication and dissemination strategy taking into account the intended audience, stakeholders, dissemination channels and opportunities, appropriate communication tools, etc. Any eventual change in D8.1 that would affect D8.2 would be implemented in the latter. D8.2 deliverable focusses on the website as a tool developed specifically to fulfil the goals of the communication plan.

2 ECHARGE4DRIVERS WEBSITE

eCharge4Drivers' project website domain name is www.echarge4drivers.eu. The website will be an important communication and dissemination tool for eCharge4Drivers, as it will contain all the necessary information on the project and will be constantly updated with the latest information. It will be the project's main channel to the outside world, providing information on eCharge4Drivers objectives, partners, methodologies, results, publications, news and success stories. As nowadays a high number of website visits happens via mobile phones, a mobile version of the website is also available.

2.1 Structure and content

eCharge4Drivers website's high-level structure has been created to display information about the project in a transparent and accessible manner. It comprises the elements below.

2.1.1 Homepage

The homepage (Figure 1 - Figure 3), being the point of entry for site visitors, presents essential project information and uses a simple layout to place focus on the branding and also to facilitate navigation. The header area contains the project's logo on the left side and the menu banner on the central-right side. The menu banner has been divided into Home, Objectives, Sites, Consortium, News & Events, Library and Contact us. The homepage is laid out as follows:

- It features a visual banner with an image representing a charging station. The image embodies the colours of the project's visual identity. Below the project's name there is a slogan, chosen by ERTICO, ICCS and POLIS: "**Easy charging, easy driving**". This slogan will serve future communications (e.g. newsletters, banners, etc) and will strengthen the project's goal and vision (Figure 1).
- The newsletter: features a section where visitors can subscribe to eCharge4Drivers' newsletter. In parallel, a mailing list on Mailchimp has been created to store the email addresses of all subscribers. Subscribers will have the option to also opt-out and stop receiving eCharge4Drivers' newsletters, as foreseen by GDPR.
- Facts and figures: features four "bubbles" with information on the duration of the project, the number of partners and countries where eCharge4Drivers will be deployed and the number of demonstration areas.
- About the project: This section outlines eCharge4Drivers' goals and how it will achieve them.
- News: this section shows a preview of the latest news published on the website.
- Twitter feed: live feed from the project's social media account.
- Contact details: provides the contact details of the project Coordinator and an email reflector for the communication and marketing aspect of eCharge4Drivers. This reflector is linked to the email addresses of ERTICO, ICCS and POLIS dissemination and communication contacts.
- Bottom banner with social media icons (Twitter and LinkedIn), the EU flag, the reference to the EU funding and copyright (present on all pages of the website).

Figure 1: Homepage with project name and slogan.

Figure 2 : Overview of the home page.

Figure 3: Bottom of the homepage.

2.1.2 Objectives

This page provides a more detailed description of the project's main objectives, each one with sub-points, as indicated in Figure 4: Overview of the Objectives page.

Figure 4: Overview of the Objectives page.

2.1.3 Sites

The page begins with an overview of the demonstration sites and TEN-T corridors involved in the project. The introduction informs website visitors about the narrative of the 10 sites and their focus, essential to reach eCharge4Drivers' goals (Figure 5).

Following this overview, the page provides information on the six urban areas and four TEN-T corridors in two separate sections. All descriptions have been drafted in collaboration with each city/TEN-T corridor involved in the project and have followed a specific scheme to ensure consistency.

(a)

(b)

Figure 5: Overview of the Sites page – TEN-T Corridors.

2.1.4 Consortium

This section offers quick access to information about the project partners (Figure 6). It contains the description, logo and link to the website of each project member. The content was drafted in collaboration with each member of the consortium, following a specific scheme, which guarantees consistency throughout all descriptions.

Figure 6: Consortium.

2.1.5 News & events

This page is divided in news at the top and events at the bottom (Figure 7 - Figure 8). Both sections show the latest three items published. By clicking on “See more news” and “See more events”, visitors can view older entries.

The news posting will follow specific criteria, such as: news about project status, reference to events, information about EV-related news etc.

News and events

Latest news

Blog post 3
 Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed do eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua. Ut enim ad minim veniam, quis nostrud exercitation ullamco laboris nisi ut aliquip ex ea commodo consequat. Duis aute inure dolor in...

08 Jul 2020

Blog post 2
 Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed do eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua. Ut enim ad minim veniam, quis nostrud exercitation ullamco laboris nisi ut aliquip ex ea commodo consequat. Duis aute inure dolor in...

08 Jul 2020

Blog 1
 Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed do eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua. Ut enim ad minim veniam, quis nostrud exercitation ullamco laboris nisi ut aliquip ex ea commodo consequat. Duis aute inure dolor in...

08 Jul 2020

Figure 7: News.

Latest events

Event 3
 Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed do eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua. Ut enim ad minim...

Jul 09, 2020

Event 2
 Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed do eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua. Ut enim ad minim...

Jul 09, 2020

Event 1
 Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed do eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua. Ut enim ad minim...

Jul 09, 2020

[See more events](#)

Figure 8: Events.

2.1.6 Library

When visiting the Library page, the visitor may select among a variety of material (Figure 9 - Figure 10). Many documents (the public deliverables, the presentations and publications) in this page will be also available for download by the consortium and any interested website user.

- Deliverables: This sub-page will display all deliverables of the project. The public deliverables and an executive summary of the confidential ones will be uploaded on the website when approved by the EC.
- In the media: this section contains mass media articles mentioning the eCharge4Drivers. The main purpose of this sub-page is to keep website visitors up to date concerning all the media news related to the project.
- Presentations: In this sub-page all the presentations carried out by the eCharge4Drivers partners in order to disseminate the project's results and developments will be available to download.
- Publications: this section contains eCharge4Drivers publications made by project partners.
- Photo gallery
- Videos

Until the project has developed content to fill each section, ERTICO will proceed with unpublishing empty sections.

Figure 9: Library.

Figure 10: Library.

2.1.7 Contact us

In addition to the contact emails present on the homepage, users can get in touch with eCharge4Drivers members via this dedicated form on the “Contact us” page (Figure 11). The form is directly linked to a dedicated email reflector, connected to ERTICO, ICCS and POLIS communication and dissemination team. This team will then make sure that the messages containing specific inquiries are redirected to the proper project member.

The “Contact us” section also includes the call for the newsletter registration.

Figure 11: Contact us.

3 PRIVACY AND COOKIE POLICY

eCharge4Drivers’ website will be compliant with the European General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). To fulfil the requirements set by this Regulation, eCharge4Drivers’ website will implement a cookie policy and a privacy policy (the privacy policy will be linked to ERTICO’s corporate website www.ertico.com). The correct use of the website visitors’ personal data will also be ensured when using Mailchimp service for the project’s newsletter. Subscribers, in fact, will be able to actively subscribe and unsubscribe to eCharge4Drivers’ newsletter at any moment. The data collected with Mailchimp will be stored throughout the project and subsequently deleted once the project ends.

4 TECHNICAL ASPECTS

eCharge4Drivers’ website has been built with WordPress, using the latest theme available: Divi. This theme allows the website manager to add, remove and change items directly from the front-end of the website.

The performance of the website will be tracked using Google Analytics (Figure 12 - Figure 14). The parameters chosen to track such performance are the number of visitors and the location from where they visit eCharge4Drivers’ website. Such parameters will provide a useful insight into the project’s communication activities, as it will reflect the outreach of the project’s communication activities.

Figure 12: Google Analytics home page.

Figure 13: Google Analytics overview of page visitors from 3 August to 8 September 2020.

Figure 14: Google Analytics overview of the location from which visitors accessed eCharge4Drivers' website between 3 August to 8 September 2020.

5 WEBSITE KPIS

KPIs (Key Performance Indicators) are a measurable value that demonstrates how effectively a company, organisation, or in this case a project, is achieving key objectives. With the Google Analytics tool, eCharge4Drivers will be able to measure its performance in terms of number of visitors of its website (including new visitors), the time spent visiting the website, the top pages visited, the country

from which users accessed the website, the language used and the tool from which the search was conducted (computer, smartphone or tablet).

As outlined in Section 8 « Monitoring Impact » of the public deliverable 8.1 (Table 1), eCharge4Drivers is expected to reach 200 visitors per month in year 2 of the project's life span, and 400 visitors per month within year 4. In terms of news items, these shall be published on eCharge4Drivers' website and be 10 or more within the second year of the project, and 40 or more within the fourth year. Publications will also be present on the website: two or more within the second year, and nine or more within the fourth year of the project.

Activity	Expected performance	
	KPI target: Year 2	KPI target: Year 4
Website – number of visitors	200/month	400/month
Twitter – number of followers	100	200
LinkedIn – number of followers	100	200
Newsletter – number of newsletters sent out	2/year	2/year
Quantity of media coverage achieved	≥10	≥40
Number of peer reviewed publications	≥2	≥9
Number of external stakeholders attending the local events	20	-
Number of final event attendees	-	100-150
Number of participants in awareness events	≥20	≥20
Number of External Interest Groups participants	≥20	≥40
Number of projects contacted	≥5	≥10
Number of liaison activities performed	≥5	≥10

Table 1: Website KPIs outlined in D8.1 [1].

ERTICO will be able to monitor eCharge4Drivers' website performance via Google Analytics.

6 CONCLUSIONS

eCharge4Drivers' website was delivered at the beginning of month 3 of the project's lifespan. The website fully embeds the visual identity set at the beginning of the project and it is built following a structure that best contains and communicates the project's resources and findings. Thanks to an easy-to-navigate website, the end user is once again at the centre of the project, in all of its aspects. In conclusion, the current website represents a good and efficient starting point on which the project can progress and build itself, and will be constantly updated as eCharge4Drivers progresses.

7 REFERENCES

- [1] eCharge4Drivers Deliverable 8.1: “Dissemination and Communication Strategy”.

